
Genetic Algorithm Learning Operators to Solve the Vehicle Routing Problem

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Abstract

In recent years, researchers have focused on solving real-world optimization problems that impact logistics and transportation. Among these, the Vehicle Routing Problem (VRP) and its various variants have gained significant attention due to their wide ranging applications. One of the most widely used techniques for solving VRP is the Genetic Algorithm (GA). As part of the Evolutionary Intelligence approaches, GA leverages its operators to learn how to adapt its prospecting of the problem search space, in order to reach efficiently good solutions. This paper provides an overview of GA operators tailored to solve VRP, and evaluates different operator configurations for the Capacitated VRP by using a benchmark set taken from the literature, to trial their learning performance.

Keywords: Evolutionary Intelligence, Combinatorial Optimization, Vehicle Routing Problem, Genetic Algorithm, Genetic operators, Selection, Crossover, Mutation.

1 Introduction

Logistics, transportation, and supply chain management have been among the key areas of research in recent years. Two fundamental optimization challenges in these domains are the Traveling Salesman Problem (TSP) and the Vehicle Routing Problem.

The TSP is a well-known combinatorial optimization problem where a salesman must visit a set of customers exactly once and return to the starting point while minimizing travel distance [1]. Over time, this concept has been extended to incorporate multiple vehicles and additional constraints beyond just minimizing the overall travel distance. This extension is known as the Vehicle Routing Problem (VRP) (Figure 1).

Figure 1: TSP vs. VRP

VRP generalizes the TSP by determining a set of vehicle routes, each assigned to serve a group of customers with known demands. The objective is to minimize the total travel distance while satisfying problem-specific constraints [2]. Due to its broad real-world applications, researchers have continuously enhanced the classical VRP model by introducing additional constraints and various optimization criteria to make it more practical.

Different VRP constraints have led to the development of multiple VRP variants such as (Figure 2):

- Capacitated VRP (CVRP): Involves a fleet of vehicles with limited capacity, where the total quantity delivered on each route must not exceed the vehicle's capacity [3, 4].
- Heterogeneous VRP (HVRP): If all vehicles have the same characteristics (e.g., volume, speed, capacity), the problem is considered homogeneous [5]; otherwise, it is heterogeneous [6].
- VRP with Time Windows (VRPTW): Considers customer availability, ensuring that deliveries are made within a predefined time window [3, 7].
- Periodic VRP (PVRP): Deals with customers who require deliveries on a recurring schedule over a specific planning horizon [8].
- Multi-Depot VRP (MDVRP): Incorporates multiple distribution centers from which vehicles are dispatched to serve customers [9].
- Open VRP (OVRP): In this variant, vehicles are not required to return to the distribution center after completing their routes[10].
- Dynamic VRP (DVRP): Unlike static VRP, this version assumes that customer requests can change in real time during the delivery process. New requests may be added, existing ones may be canceled, or delivery conditions may change, requiring continuous route re-optimization [10, 11].

Figure 2: Some VRP variations

The objective function in VRP varies depending on the problem context. It may be defined by using one of the following criteria or a combination of them:

- minimize total distance,
- minimize travel cost,
- minimize penalties,
- maximize customer satisfaction,
- maximize service quality.

These criteria will be revisited with full details in section 2.3

Over the years, various solution approaches have been proposed to tackle the complexity of different VRP variants. These approaches are broadly classified into exact and approximate methods. Since VRP is NP-hard, and thus, finding an optimal solution for large instances is computationally expensive, exact methods become impractical for large-scale problems. Instead, approximate methods (heuristics and meta-heuristics) are the preferred choice. Among them, Genetic Algorithms (GA) have gained popularity due to their ability to explore large solution spaces efficiently and produce high-quality solutions.

In VRP applications, the performance of Genetic Algorithms can be boosted or hindered by the operators to be used, which directly influence solution quality. Indeed, GA operators give the GA its ability to learn from generation to generation how to correct its trajectory towards promising areas of the solutions' search space. This paper surveys the different GA operators applied to solve VRP.

The remainder of this paper is organized as follows: Section 2 provides an overview of the Genetic Algorithm. Section 3 presents different GA operators applied to VRP, Sections 4 and 5 describe the experimental methodology and the results and discussion, respectively. Finally, Section 4 concludes the paper with insights and future research directions.

2 Genetic Algorithm learning mechanism

Genetic Algorithms are a class of metaheuristic optimization techniques inspired by the principles of natural selection and evolution, as described by Charles Darwin [12, 13, 14]. GAs, even in their basic form, embody key concepts of Artificial Intelligence as they can *learn*, *adapt* and *search* for good solutions to problems difficult to solve by humans. GAs are particularly effective in solving complex optimization problems by intelligently exploring the search space and finding optimal or near-optimal solutions within a reasonable time frame. This makes GAs highly useful for NP-hard problems, such as the Vehicle Routing Problem and its variants.

GAs work by maintaining a population of candidate solutions that can learn across multiple generations through the application of genetic operators, including selection, crossover, and mutation. These operations guide the search towards high-quality solutions.

2.1 Key concepts in GAs

To understand how GAs function, the following fundamental concepts should be introduced [15, 16]:

- Population: A set of chromosomes, each representing a potential solution to the problem.
- Chromosome: An encoded representation of a solution in a specific format (e.g., sequence of customer visits in VRP).
- Gene: A component of a chromosome that represents a decision variable (e.g., a customer or a route segment).
- Allele: A specific value that a gene can take.
- Offspring: New chromosomes produced through crossover and mutation operations.
- Objective function: A function that evaluates the fitness (quality) of each solution, based on the problem's optimization goal (e.g., minimizing total travel cost).

2.2 Genetic Algorithm process

The standard process of a GA follows these steps (Figure 3) [17]:

1. Initialization: Generate an initial population of candidate solutions, either randomly or using problem-specific heuristics.
2. Evaluation: Compute the fitness of each chromosome in the population using the objective function.
3. Selection: Choose parent solutions from the population based on their fitness values, ensuring that better solutions have a higher chance of being selected.
4. Reproduction (Crossover & Mutation):
 - Crossover: Combine genetic material from two parent solutions to generate offspring.
 - Mutation: Introduce small random modifications to maintain diversity in the population.
5. Replacement: Replace some or all of the existing population with newly generated offspring, forming the next generation.

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6. Termination condition: Check if a predefined stopping criterion is met (e.g., reaching a maximum number of generations, convergence of solutions, or stability in fitness values). If the criterion is met, return the best chromosome as the final solution; otherwise, repeat the process from step 2.

Figure 3: Genetic algorithm flowchart

2.3 Optimization Criteria in VRP

The Vehicle Routing Problem encompasses a variety of optimization objectives, which vary depending on the problem variant and practical application domain. Traditionally, the primary objective in VRP is to minimize the total distance travelled or to optimize the number of routes (vehicles). However, many real-world scenarios introduce additional or alternative goals, such as minimizing total travel time, reducing fuel consumption, balancing the workload among vehicles, or maximizing customer satisfaction by respecting service time windows and delivery preferences.

When applying Genetic Algorithms to solve VRP, the fitness function is a critical component that encodes these objectives into a quantifiable criterion. Depending on the VRP variant, the fitness function can be single-objective (minimizing total cost) or multi-objective (minimizing cost while maximizing service quality), and often involves penalization terms for constraint violations such as time windows. For instance, VRP with Time Window and Capacitated VRP, infeasible solutions may be penalized based on the degree of violation. Furthermore, the GA must be carefully tailored to preserve feasibility during the search process while maintaining diversity in the population. By clearly defining and incorporating these objectives into the evolution process and evaluation mechanisms, GA can effectively explore the solution space and adapt to different VRP scenarios.

2.4 Learning mechanisms in Genetic Algorithms

Since Genetic Algorithms are inspired by biological evolution they are designed to adapt their behaviour over time, a property often referred to as learning.

This feature is further stressed in Adaptive GAs, where the probabilities of applying genetic operators (selection, crossover, mutation) are dynamically adjusted based on their historical performance across generations. This process enables the algorithm to emphasize the most successful operators, improving convergence speed and maintaining population diversity [18].

Self-adaptive GAs go a step further by encoding control parameters directly into the chromosomes, allowing these parameters to evolve alongside the solutions themselves. This mechanism enables the algorithm to autonomously learn optimal operator settings and adjust to the characteristics of the problem over time [19]. For example, in dynamic VRPs, such approaches automatically increase mutation rates when new customer requests arrive, enabling faster adaptation to changing conditions.

Recently, hybrid approaches have combined self-adaptation with reinforcement learning or deep learning to further enhance the algorithm's ability to navigate complex and dynamic search spaces. These learning-driven strategies are particularly valuable in solving real-world optimization problems such as the Vehicle Routing Problem, where constraints and environmental conditions can vary significantly. Such mechanisms highlight the potential of learning-enabled GAs to intelligently and autonomously explore the solution space, aligning with the goal of achieving robust and efficient optimization in logistics and transportation.

Different Genetic Algorithm operators are designed for specific problem domains. The next section surveys the GA operators commonly applied to VRP.

3 GA operators for VRP

The effectiveness of GAs in solving the Vehicle Routing Problem largely depends on the choice and implementation of the genetic operators. These operators play a crucial role in guiding the search process, maintaining population diversity, and ensuring convergence toward high quality solutions. While the fundamental GA operators (selection, crossover, and mutation) are common across different optimization problems, their adaptation to VRP requires specialized mechanisms to handle route based representations, feasibility constraints, and solution quality. Various modifications of selection, crossover, and mutation have been proposed in the literature to enhance GA performance in VRP. After presenting the initial steps of the GA to solve VRP, the most widely used operators are described in what follows.

3.1 Chromosome representation

The encoding method directly impacts GA's ability to find optimal or near-optimal solutions efficiently. The chromosome representation in GA is crucial for determining good solutions to VRP. However, discussing all the encoding approaches is beyond the scope of this work. Instead, we present the presentation that allows to understand the described operators.

Among the various encoding techniques proposed in the literature, *path representation* is the most widely used for VRP. In this approach[14]:

- Customers are represented by integer identifiers, with each integer corresponding to a specific customer
- The order of these integers within the chromosome defines the sequence of customer visits
- The Depot Index (typically 0) indicates the start and end points of each route, segmenting the chromosome into separate routes
- Each route is marked by a depot index, with customers visited in the order specified by the sequence of integers

This encoding structure provides a direct and clear representation of customer visit sequences and vehicle routes, as shown in Figure 4a. After constructing the full chromosome, depot indexes can be removed to improve readability, as demonstrated in Figure 4b.

(a) with depot index

(b) without depot index

Figure 4: VRP chromosome representations

3.2 Selection operators

The selection process in GAs determines which individuals (solutions) are chosen for reproduction. While no specific selection method is designed exclusively for the Vehicle Routing Problem (VRP) and its variants, the following widely used selection operators can be effectively applied:

- **Roulette wheel selection (RWS):** assigns a probability to each chromosome based on its fitness. A virtual wheel is spun, and the chromosome closest to the stopping point is selected. Since elements with higher fitness occupy a larger portion of the wheel, they have a greater chance of being chosen[20].
- **Elitism selection (ES):** preserves the best solutions by directly transferring them to the next generation, ensuring that high-quality solutions are not lost during the evolutionary process [14].
- **Rank selection (RS):** orders chromosomes based on fitness and assigns selection probabilities accordingly. This method prevents highly fit individuals from dominating the selection process too early, leading to a more balanced exploration of the solution space [14].
- **Tournament selection (TS):** involves randomly selecting a subset of chromosomes and conducting a competition, where the one with the highest fitness is chosen. This method maintains diversity and prevents premature convergence to local optima [14].

3.3 Crossover operators

The crossover process in genetic algorithms mimics a natural biological phenomenon where genetic material is exchanged between parents to create offspring. The most fundamental crossover methods are *one-point crossover* and *two-point crossover*.

In one-point crossover, a random cutting point along the chromosome is selected, and the segments of the chromosome are exchanged between two parent chromosomes [12]. In two-point crossover, two cutting points are selected, and the portion between these points is swapped between the parents [13].

While these methods are simple and intuitive, they are often not well-suited for combinatorial optimization problems like the Traveling Salesman Problem (TSP) and Vehicle Routing Problem (VRP). One of the main issues is that these basic crossover methods can generate duplicate genes or customer visits within the chromosomes, which is a critical problem in TSP and VRP, where each customer must be visited exactly once in a valid solution. As a result, offspring created through these methods may require post-crossover repair to remove duplicates and restore feasibility.

To address these limitations, several advanced and specialized crossover techniques have been developed. These methods aim to preserve the validity of the solution, ensuring that the offspring generated do not violate the constraints (such as visiting each customer exactly once) and enhancing the efficiency of the genetic search process. Some of the key techniques are:

- **Order crossover:** This recombination technique is designed for permutation-based problems such as the VRP. It preserves the relative ordering of cities by transferring a contiguous segment from one parent while filling the remaining positions with elements from the second parent in their original

sequence, ensuring that no duplicates occur. The process begins with the selection of two cut points, defining a subsequence to be directly copied into the offspring. The remaining positions are then filled by sequentially inserting elements from the other parent, starting immediately after the second cut point and skipping those already present in the offspring (see Figure 5) [20, 21, 22].

Figure 5: Order crossover

- Cycle crossover: this method used for permutation problems. It works by identifying cycles of genes between two parent solutions and transferring them to the offspring. The process starts by copying genes from Parent 1 to the offspring, then follows the positions of corresponding genes in Parent 2 to complete the cycle. Once a cycle is finished, the remaining genes are copied from the other parent. This ensures a valid permutation without duplicates, preserving the relative order of genes from both parents. It's particularly useful for problems like TSP or VRP. (see Figure 6) [23, 24, 25].

Figure 6: Cycle crossover

- Partially mapped crossover: This method works by selecting a random subsequence from one parent and copying it into the offspring. The remaining positions in the offspring are filled with genes from the other parent in the order they appear, while preserving the relative order of the cities from the first parent. This technique avoids duplicates and preserves the structure of the parent solutions (see Figure 7) [26, 27].

Figure 7: Partially mapped crossover

- Order based crossover: This method begins by randomly selecting a set of positions in Parent 1. Next, the genes from Parent 2 are copied into Child 1, excluding the genes located in the

selected positions of Parent 1. Finally, loop over parent 1 and transfer to child 1 the genes that are not already transferred to it. This ensures that the offspring maintains a valid permutation and preserves key structural properties from both parents. (see Figure 8) [28, 29, 30].

Figure 8: Order based crossover

3.4 Mutation operators

Many mutation types are proposed in the literature, such as:

- Exchange (or Swap) mutation: This mutation operator randomly selects two cities in the tour and exchanges their positions as shown in Figure 9a [31, 23, 32].
- Insertion mutation: The insertion mutation operator randomly chooses a city in the tour, removes it from this tour, and inserts it in a randomly selected place as shown in Figure 9b [33, 34].
- Inversion mutation: This operator randomly selects a sub-tour, removes it from the tour, then inserts it in reversed order at a randomly selected position (see Figure 9c) [33, 35, 34].

(a) Exchange

(b) Insertion

Selecting 3 to be inserted after 6

(c) Inversion

Select sequence (4,5,6) and insert it after 2

Figure 9: Mutation operators

4 Experimental Methodology

To support the theoretical analysis of genetic algorithm (GA) operators, namely, selection, mutation, and crossover, this study conducted a set of experiments evaluating various combinations of these operators. In total, 48 distinct GA configurations are examined. The objective is to assess the influence of these operators on the algorithms performance in solving the Capacitated Vehicle Routing Problem (CVRP), using a well-established benchmark set [36].

Our experimental analysis focuses on the A-n32-k5 instance, which is characterized by the following features:

- 31 customer locations, each associated with a specific demand.
- A homogeneous fleet consisting of 5 vehicles with identical capacity.
- A known optimal total distance of 784 kilometers.

The experimental setup adopted in this study includes:

- Population size: 100 individuals.
- Maximum number of generations: 500.
- Constraint-handling strategy: penalty functions are applied to penalize individuals that violate the problem’s constraints, including capacity limitations and the number of available vehicles.

5 Results and Discussion

The results in Table 1 demonstrate significant variability in performance across the 48 genetic operator combinations. Notably, the OBX crossover paired with inversion mutation and elite selection achieved the lowest distance of 838.42 km, which is close to the benchmarks optimal distance (784 km) by just 6.9%. This configuration also exhibited moderate computation time (4.69 s), suggesting a favourable balance between solution quality and computational effort. Conversely, configurations using CX crossover with insertion mutation (1214.52 km) highlight the risks of poor operator synergy, where premature convergence and limited exploration lead to suboptimal solutions.

Table 2 underscores the superiority of OBX crossover, which achieved both the lowest best-case distance (838.42 km) and the lowest average (950.11 km). In contrast, CX crossover exhibited the highest worst-case distance (1214.52 km) and average (1025.71 km), indicating instability in maintaining solution quality.

Table 2: Distance results for Crossover operators

Crossover operator	Best	Worst	Average
PMX	875.50	1183.41	1016.87
OX	897.57	1089.07	984.62
OBX	838.42	1143.70	950.11
CX	870.60	1214.52	1025.71

Additionally, Table 3 summarizes the performance of each mutation operator across all selection and crossover combinations. The inversion mutation yielded the most promising results overall, providing both the lowest best-case distance and the lowest average distance. This demonstrates its advantage in maintaining solution quality while efficiently exploring the solution space.

Table 3: Performances of Mutation operators

Mutation operator	Best	Worst	Average
Insertion	967.48	1214.52	1059.82
Swap	863.99	1146.60	960.86
Inversion	838.42	1178.33	962.25

Table 1: Performance evaluation of genetic operator combinations on the CVRP (Instance A-n32-k5)

Genetic Operators			Performance Metrics		
Crossover	Mutation	Selection	Distance (Km)	Time (s)	Convergence
PMX	Insertion	Elite	1005.27	4.58	51
PMX	Insertion	Tournament	1054.96	2.38	493
PMX	Insertion	Roulette	1183.41	2.62	379
PMX	Insertion	Rank	1047.46	4.53	491
PMX	Swap	Elite	1001.64	5.16	69
PMX	Swap	Tournament	929.07	2.26	257
PMX	Swap	Roulette	1146.60	2.56	460
PMX	Swap	Rank	921.60	5.50	491
PMX	Inversion	Elite	946.69	3.55	74
PMX	Inversion	Tournament	875.50	2.42	440
PMX	Inversion	Roulette	1178.33	2.71	492
PMX	Inversion	Rank	911.89	5.59	491
OX	Insertion	Elite	1010.58	3.66	70
OX	Insertion	Tournament	1014.45	2.50	478
OX	Insertion	Roulette	1013.40	3.50	437
OX	Insertion	Rank	976.00	4.77	390
OX	Swap	Elite	916.75	3.68	100
OX	Swap	Tournament	1047.53	2.80	481
OX	Swap	Roulette	1067.24	3.64	462
OX	Swap	Rank	897.57	4.52	459
OX	Inversion	Elite	977.26	3.84	94
OX	Inversion	Tournament	903.68	3.72	487
OX	Inversion	Roulette	1089.07	2.73	457
OX	Inversion	Rank	901.89	4.50	497
OBX	Insertion	Elite	1143.70	4.52	63
OBX	Insertion	Tournament	1018.18	2.25	486
OBX	Insertion	Roulette	996.05	2.42	439
OBX	Insertion	Rank	1035.97	4.18	393
OBX	Swap	Elite	917.28	4.51	111
OBX	Swap	Tournament	863.99	2.20	486
OBX	Swap	Roulette	918.42	2.38	430
OBX	Swap	Rank	894.42	4.16	486
OBX	Inversion	Elite	838.42	4.69	73
OBX	Inversion	Tournament	872.04	2.29	309
OBX	Inversion	Roulette	983.75	2.43	401
OBX	Inversion	Rank	919.11	4.89	417
CX	Insertion	Elite	1214.52	6.06	40
CX	Insertion	Tournament	967.48	3.60	323
CX	Insertion	Roulette	1127.22	4.50	461
CX	Insertion	Rank	1149.44	5.35	464
CX	Swap	Elite	1005.40	6.61	39
CX	Swap	Tournament	899.72	4.13	468
CX	Swap	Roulette	1034.52	3.73	483
CX	Swap	Rank	911.94	7.04	465
CX	Inversion	Elite	956.47	5.65	81
CX	Inversion	Tournament	870.60	4.51	490
CX	Inversion	Roulette	1115.62	3.59	487
CX	Inversion	Rank	1055.63	5.44	492

Note: All solutions are feasible and utilize all 5 vehicles. Distances reflect total route lengths in kilometers. The Convergence column indicates the generation at which the best solution was first identified.

Regarding selection mechanisms, Table 4 illustrates that elitism consistently helped in preserving high-quality individuals, while tournament selection offered a good balance between exploration and exploitation. Roulette and rank selection performed moderately, with less consistent results.

Table 4: Summary Statistics for Selection Operators

Selection operator	Best	Worst	Average
Elite	838.42	1214.52	994.50
Tournament	863.99	1054.96	943.10
Roulette	918.42	1183.41	1071.05
Rank	894.42	1149.44	968.58

The top performing configurations in Table 5 highlight the dominance of OBX crossover and inversion mutation, which appear in three and four of the five best combinations, respectively. The prevalence of tournament selection (four entries) alongside elite selection (one entry) further supports its role in maintaining population diversity. Notably, the winning configuration (OBX + inversion + elite) achieved a 6.9% deviation from the benchmarks optimal distance, demonstrating the potential of carefully tuned GAs for near-optimal CVRP solutions.

These results validate the critical role of operator selection in GA performance. The synergy between OBX crossover, inversion mutation, and tournament/elite selection emerges as a robust strategy for CVRP optimization.

Table 5: Top 5 Genetic Operator Combinations by Distance

Crossover	Mutation	Selection	Distance
OBX	Inversion	Elite	838.42
OBX	Swap	Tournament	863.99
CX	Inversion	Tournament	870.60
OBX	Inversion	Tournament	872.04
OX	Inversion	Tournament	903.68

6 Conclusion

The Vehicle Routing Problem (VRP) is a well-known problem extensively studied in the literature due to its wide-ranging practical applications. VRP is NP-hard. As a result, approximate methods, such as Genetic Algorithms (GAs), which are a key component of the Evolutionary Intelligence portfolio, offer a more viable solution approach for larger-scale problems.

Inspired from the evolution process of natural species, GAs can learn to adapt themselves by leveraging its operators capability to find and maintain good genetic information from generation to generation. In this paper, we reviewed various GA operators specifically designed for the VRP and its variants. The empirical evaluation of various operator configurations on the Capacitated VRP using a well-known benchmark set demonstrated that the combination OBX crossover, inversion mutation, and tournament selection achieve near-optimal results, deviating by only 6.9% from the benchmarks theoretical optimum.

As a prospective extension of this work, we recommend applying the tested operator configurations across a broader range of benchmark datasets and VRP variants. Such an extension would facilitate a comparative analysis aimed at assessing the operators' robustness and generalization ability with respect to solution quality. This comparative analysis could provide valuable insights into the learning strength of each operator for solving VRP variants effectively.

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